

IP4MaaS

Deliverable D5.5 Final report on Osijek demonstration execution

Project acronym:	IP4MaaS
Starting date:	01/12/2020
Duration (in months):	31 months
Call (part) identifier:	S2R-OC-IP4-01-2020
Grant agreement no:	101015492
Due date of deliverable:	Month 30
Actual submission date:	15-09-2023
Responsible/Author:	DYVOLVE
Dissemination level:	PU
Status:	Issued

Reviewed: (yes)

Document history		
<i>Revision</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	16/06/2023	First issue
2	29/06/2023	Second issue
3	05/07/2023	Submission
4	21/08/2023	Resubmission after rejection
5	15/09/2023	2 nd resubmission after rejection

Report contributors		
Name	Beneficiary Short Name	Details of contribution
DYVOLVE Ltd.	DYV	Osijek demo leader - report preparation
OLTIS	OLT	Official Review
CERTH	CERTH	Official Review

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1. Executive Summary

The aim of the Deliverable 5.5 “Final report on Osijek Demonstration execution” is to present the timeline and details of the preparation and execution of Osijek Demonstration taking place in the framework of the IP4MaaS project within the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking. The demonstrated technologies were selected functionalities of the Travel Companion application.

The demonstration consisted testing the Travel Companion application to a group of recruited users who were given a link to download and install the application, use it while travelling by means of GPP Osijek (buses and trams) and by shared bikes and e-bikes, and provide feedback regarding the selected functionalities. Testers provided feedback using the online User Satisfaction Index questionnaire form. The USI questionnaire was developed as part of the WP3, task T3.2 “User satisfaction with IP4 solutions”.

Major contribution of Osijek demo preparation and execution was the integration of public transport and bike sharing services in Osijek into the journey planning tool.

Deliverable 5.5 outlines the various activities that took place as part of coordination, preparation, and execution of the Osijek demonstration, reports the contribution of the Osijek demonstration team to technological integration, reports the internal testing of the integrated technology and the outcomes and findings of the Osijek demonstration activities.

2. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
CFM	Calls for Members
DL	Demo leader
EU	European Union
FS	Financial Statement
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
MaaS	Mobility As a Service
OC	Open Call
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
PT	Public Transport
QAC	Quality Assurance Committee
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
TC	Travel Companion
TL	Technical leader
TSP	Transport Service Provider
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work package leader

3. Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D5.5 “Final report on Osijek demonstration execution” of the T5.5 “Osijek demonstration” of the WP5 in the framework of the IP4MaaS project (GA number 101015492, S2R-OC-IP4-01-2020) under the Innovation Programme 4 (IP4) of the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking, executed in cooperation with Call for Members Consortia COHESIVE (GA 777599, S2R-CFM-IP4-02-2017), CONNECTIVE (GA 777522, S2R-CFM-IP4-01-2017) and ExtenSive (GA 101015462, S2R-CFM-IP4-01-2020) also being a part of the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking and connected with the IP4MaaS Consortium by means of the Collaboration Agreement.

The results and conclusions of the Osijek demo execution presented in this document also contribute to T5.1 of the IP4MaaS project – "Coordination of the demonstrations executions" and corresponding D5.1 "Results of the demonstrations". Results contribute to WP6 D6.2 "Performance assessment".

4. Objective/Aim

This document describes the preparation, execution, and results of the Osijek demo within task T5.5, “Osijek demonstration” of the WP5 “Demonstration Execution Support” of the IP4MaaS project.

The IP4MaaS project aim is to promote the adoption of Mobility as a Service (MaaS) schemes by testing the technologies developed within the IP4 Shift2Rail through six demonstrations conducted in Europe: Athens, Barcelona, Liberec, **Osijek**, Padua, and Warsaw. The aim of the document is to describe:

- the Osijek demo objectives and purposes,
- the process and development of the Osijek demo through dedicated meetings and workshops aimed to coordinate and foster the demo preparation and execution,
- the demonstrated functionalities and selection process of the functionalities integrated for the Osijek demo,
- the development of the User Engagement Strategy that was designed and implemented by the Osijek demo team,
- the internal coordination and internal testing of the Travel Companion application,
- the training of the testers of the Travel Companion application (engagement event),
- the reporting of the issues regarding the Travel Companion application,
- the Osijek execution phase: the number of registered testers, used functionalities, structure, and satisfaction of testers with functionalities, the number of USI questionnaires delivered, etc., and
- the lessons learned.

5. General information about demonstration site

Osijek demo site covered the area where the GPP Osijek public transport service/network is available and areas where bike sharing service is available. The covered area included the City of Osijek and its surrounding municipalities Antunovac, Čepin, and Erdut (Bijelo Brdo).

- **Demo site area:** the City of Osijek and surrounding municipalities with available PT
- **Execution period:** 29.05.2023 - 02.06.2023
- **Target groups:** students and PT users
- **Demo site leader:** Dyvolve
- **Number of TSPs integrated:** 2; GPP Osijek & partner Nextbike
- **Registered testers:** 43
- **Number of USI survey respondents:** 41
- **Functionalities tested:** 10

The Osijek demo site stakeholders that prepared, coordinated, and executed the demo were:

- **Dyvolve** (Osijek demo leader (DL)) represented by Mr. Domagoj Majcan, Mr. Božo Cicvarić, Mr. Gordan Topolovec, and Mr. Saša Bart,
- **Gradski prijevoz putnika d.o.o. Osijek (GPP Osijek)** (public tram and bus TSP) represented by Mr. Behar Rečica, Mr. Goran Pajnić, and
- **Nextbike** (e-bike and bike sharing service provider) represented Mr. Ante Gustin.

At the beginning of the IP4MaaS project, HŽ Putnički prijevoz (HŽPP) confirmed their interest and support during the project by signing the Letter of Support in 2020. During the IP4MaaS project activities, new management board of HŽPP made a business decision to start upgrading their own ticketing & issuance systems (off- and on-board ticketing, travel planner and ticketing management mobile app, etc.), which limited their ability to participate in this project actively. Due to the technology upgrade of their aforementioned systems, HŽPP couldn't support and integrate third party solutions at the time of IP4MaaS project activities, which were planned for the Osijek demo. Therefore, changes and amendments had to be made for the planned Osijek demo site integrations. Yet, HŽPP have stayed and still are open to assess IP4MaaS project and Osijek demo site results and integrate them into future service offerings.

In terms of the involvement of Academic institutions as stakeholders, mainly the University of J.J. Strossmayer (the largest public university in the Eastern Croatia, with faculties in Osijek), their engagement focus was on projected involvement of their students in demo activities (as one of the main user groups of public transport).

Osijek demo goals:

- To test and demonstrate Shift2Rail IP4 functionalities by connecting different back-end systems (GPP & Nextbike APIs) and provide added value to public transport users,
- To explore the potentials of creating a MaaS ecosystem through multimodal trip planning by using Journey planning, My trips, Navigation, etc., and
- To test and demonstrate the integration of traditional modes of public transport (trams and buses) with innovative new services (e-bike & bike sharing).

Achievement of the goals mentioned above contributed to achieving the main goal: to gain the knowledge and experience of creating a MaaS ecosystem and ultimately speed up the future uptake of MaaS technologies.

6. Preparation phase

Prior to the start of the Osijek demo preparation phase, as part of the earlier project activities (in WP2), different stakeholder groups were involved in the AS-IS/TO-BE scenarios workshop organized to define and co-create the use-cases. Stakeholder groups / data sources consisted of:

- Local government of the City of Osijek,
- GPP (local TSP) different business units,
- Student representatives of the local University of J.J. Strossmayer,
- Osijek Local SMEs and City-owned companies (their employees as PT users).

All inputs were analysed and used to define High-level user journeys, AS-IS user journey maps, and User needs (all documented in “D2.2 Demonstration Requirements and Scenarios” to serve as one of the inputs toward the Osijek demo preparation.

The Osijek demo **preparation phase consisted of the following activities:**

- Regular communication and coordination regarding the demo preparation (internal - between demo team members, and external - with WPL and with CFM),
- Creation of a demo time plan and task division between DL, GPP Osijek, and Nextbike,
- Creation and regular update of tasks checklist in Excel with assigned task owners,
- Preparation of multimodal test cases for the Osijek demo site,
- Preparation and translation of all the necessary documentation to Croatian language (*Travel Companion application (TC app), Terms & conditions, TC user guide, USI survey*),
- Risk assessment and assigned mitigation measures mainly related to fulfilling the technical prerequisites for the demo (necessary data and APIs preparation),
- Fulfilling technical prerequisites for successful functionalities' integration:
 - Preparation and update of GPP Osijek's GTFS and GeoJSON files and providing access to data sources through API,
 - Established cooperation between GPP and Nextbike and fulfilment of technical prerequisites (API access) for the integration of bike-sharing service, and
 - Preparation of OTP Journey Planner for the integration by OLTIS (WPL),
- Selection of the TC functionalities to be tested in the Osijek demo based on technical feasibility,
- Preparation of user engagement strategy,
- Internal testing of the TC app and final selection of TC functionalities based on the results,
- Providing feedback to the CFM through the Mantis bug reporting tool,
- Preparing materials/PPT and scenarios for the training of the testers,
- Organisation of the onsite engagement event with testers in Osijek, and
- Management and communication with demo testers via e-mails and social media.

Figure 1: Osijek demo time frame (green colour represents main preparation activities)

6.1. Demonstrated functionalities

The Travel Companion application version tested in Osijek was "TravelCompanion-r156-demo-regular-release.apk". It was provided by CFMs partners to the demo leader/WP5 leader.

The initial set of Travel Companion functionalities [1] planned for Osijek demo included Journey Planning and Navigation, focusing on multimodal trip planning. However, after internal testing, the Osijek demo team decided to test other functionalities also available in the TC app. A comprehensive list of all tested functionalities in Osijek is shown in the Table 1 below. GPP supplied the functionalities with GTFS data and data acquired from bike-sharing service provider Nextbike (GPP and Nextbike APIs).

Table 1: List of Travel Companion functionalities planned for Osijek demo

List of Travel Companion functionalities planned for Osijek demo		
16	Guest User	The function for using the application as a guest, i.e. without logging in, which allows a TC user to use limited functionalities of the personal application, e.g., quick trip planning including features such as navigation.
1	Journey Planner / Offer Builder	Calculates multimodal routes from origin to destination, involving different traditional modes of transport (tram and bus) and innovative last mile services (e.g., e-bike and bike sharing).
A1-5-6-7	Journey Planning - New functionalities: Trip Planning Hierarchy, Improved Intermodal Travel, Improved Travel Shopping, Individual Last Mile	<p>Trip Planning Hierarchy - Adding a hierarchy for the presentation of the increasing variety of results in intermodal trip planning (e.g., by transport mode or TSP)</p> <p>Improved Intermodal Travel - To improve intermodal travel solutions calculated by the Travel</p>

List of Travel Companion functionalities planned for Osijek demo		
		<p>Shopping, it will enable private transport to be the main part (in the middle of) the travel solution.</p> <p>Improved Travel Shopping - Journey Planning will find trips and offers according to multiple criteria Pareto-optimization.</p> <p>Individual Last Mile - Individual trips of user will be enriched by the existing router for individual transport (walk, bike, car) to serve the first and last mile for an end-to-end travel experience. Improved Travel shopping</p>
10	Navigation	Provides guidance on the traveller's trip. The function to navigate to the correct tram or bus stop based on the user's position, including the interchanges among different means of transport (e.g., bike sharing and tram/bus stations).
12	Trip Sharing	The function for sharing an ongoing trip and journey updates to other users.
14	Travel Arrangement	The function for planning trips for other application users.
11	Traveller's Feedback	The function for submitting or providing feedback about delays, cleanness of stations, disruptions, and crowdedness in public transportation or road environment that might be helpful for other travellers.
17	Preferences and Profiles	The function for customizing the application and setting different travel preferences such as payment method, special needs, favourite mode, seat selection, refund, and monitoring trip.
13	Group travelling/Group creation	Group Admin can set up a group and invite group members (without Group Ticket purchase option).
-	Trip price overview	The function for calculating trip price and informing a TC user about a ticket price for public transport on certain calculated routes. NOTE: Only informal purpose; no purchase option is available.

What was tested in Osijek?

Travel Companion functionalities available in the Osijek demo:

Figure 2: Illustration of tested functionalities in Osijek demo site

6.2. User engagement strategy

The User engagement strategy for the Osijek demo site consisted of the **following activities**:

1. Communication via e-mails, video conference, and phone calls between demo leader Dyvolve, GPP Osijek, Nextbike, City of Osijek, WPL, CFM, and other supporting parties.
2. GPP and the City of Osijek sent digital leaflets with a call and instructions for the TC app testing via e-mail to the faculties of the University of J.J Strossmayer (largest university in eastern Croatia, with 14 different faculties) to find testers (students and existing public transport users).
3. All faculty chairs in the University were contacted in order to facilitate engagement of their respective student in the testing phase. Leaflets were printed and posted in all University faculties' facilities to increase students' engagement as demo testers.
4. Academic sector was involved as a stakeholder in this project only in terms of projected involvement of their students in demo activities. Overall support during this campaign was given by the faculties' chairs and relevant professors in their class session, all to further engage student population.
5. Promotional campaign for Osijek demo - posts on social media:
 - a. GPP's Facebook post with demo testing invitation leaflet on May 18th and 22nd, 2023
 - b. GPP's Instagram post with demo testing invitation leaflet on May 18th, 2023.

6. After registration, GPP sent (via e-mail) registered testers an invitation to the engagement event, a user manual (in Croatian), bike sharing vouchers and credentials for the TC app installation and usage.
7. GPP also provided information to testers about the reward (free one-month GPP PT ticket).
8. DL and GPP organized an engagement/visibility event (training session) with testers and other interested parties to introduce them to the demo (on May 26th, 2023).

Figure 3: Screenshot of GPP's Instagram post about Osijek demo containing digital demo leaflet

Figure 4: Screenshot of GPP's Facebook post about Osijek demo containing digital demo leaflet

The figure below shows a digital leaflet that GPP Osijek and DL prepared to attract TC app testers.

Pilot testiranje

Traveling companion

Nova jedinstvena aplikacija za Europsko tržište

- pregledajte mogućnosti putovanja raznim modovima prijevoza putnika,
- planirajte cjelokupno putovanje kombiniranjem različitih modova prijevoza (tramvaj, autobus, bicikl i ostalo) uz kartografski prikaz i pregled točaka interesa u bilo kojem trenutku,
- pohranite omiljena putovanja i podijelite ih s drugim korisnicima.

Iskoristite
...mogućnosti nove IP4MaaS Travel Companion aplikacije kako biste došli do bilo kojeg odredišta kombinirajući različita prijevozna sredstva, od javnog prijevoza do električnih bicikala.

Probni rad
...aplikaciju možete testirati u razdoblju od tjedan dana počevši od 29. svibnja do 2. lipnja 2023. te sudjelovati u procesu njezine optimizacije ispunjavanjem upitnika o korisničkom iskustvu. Aplikacija je namijenjena korisnicima Android pametnih uređaja.
Krajnji rok za prijavu na testiranje aplikacije je 24.5.2023.

Osvojite nagradu
...ispunite evaluacijski upitnik aplikacije IP4MaaS Travel Companion na kraju vašeg testiranja i osvojite nagradu u obliku mjesečne karte GPP-a.

Koraci za registraciju za testne korisnike*

1. Za sudjelovanje u testiranju aplikacije prijavite se na e-mail adresu ip4maas@gpp-osijek.com (navedite ime i prezime, model pametnog telefona).
2. Na svoju e-mail adresu zaprimiti ćete potvrdu o sudjelovanju zajedno s uputama za instalaciju, pristupnim podacima za prijavu te uputama za korištenje aplikacije

* broj testnih korisnika je ograničen

Figure 5: Digital leaflet with a call and registration steps for TC app testing prepared by GPP Osijek in cooperation with demo leader Dyvolve

6.3. Internal coordination

Internal coordination was mainly done between Osijek demo team members and WPL. The coordination included the following activities:

- Participation of Osijek demo team members in monthly WP5 coordination online calls organized by WPL, from December 2021 to May 2023 (status checks for each demo site, WP5 updates, and discussion about risks and challenges),
- Regular weekly online calls between Osijek demo team members and WPL in April and May 2023 (updates on Osijek demo progress presented in the Excel checklist of tasks with assigned task owners, task priority, deadlines, completion status, and comments),
- Participation in meetings and workshops with the CFMs and the consortium,
- Regular and ad-hoc phone calls and online calls between Osijek demo team members,
- Regular correspondence via e-mail between Osijek demo team members, WPL, and all relevant parties in all matters regarding the IP4MaaS project and Osijek demo preparation.

Table 2: List of Osijek demo partners, their roles, and responsibilities

Demo partner	Role	Responsibilities
Dyvolve	Osijek demo leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supervision and coordination of all Osijek demo preparatory activities, tasks, and deadlines, • Active participation in Osijek demo activities, • Status check reporting and cooperation with WPL and CFMs, • Preparation of all relevant project documents and reports, • Osijek demo risk management/mitigation, • Internal TC testing and issue reporting, and • Translations of all necessary documents/features into Croatian language.
GPP Osijek	TSP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support, feedback, and active participation in Osijek demo preparatory activities, • Support in the preparation of relevant project documents and reports, • Establishing technical prerequisites for the demo (preparation and update of necessary data (GTFS) and API for the demo, etc.), • Publishing information about the Osijek demo, and providing feedback about testers' registrations to Dyvolve, and • Distributing incentives to engaged testers.
Nextbike	Bike sharing TSP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing data and access (API) for the integration of bike sharing service with other modes of transport, and • Providing vouchers for bike sharing services during demo testing.

6.4. Internal testing

The internal app testing for the Osijek demo took place **between the 4th and 26th of May 2023**. Osijek demo team members downloaded and used the TC application on different mobile devices and Android operating systems, focusing on the functionalities selected for the Osijek demo. DL

and TSP GPP communicated with respective CFM representatives almost daily. They provided feedback about the testing, including a description of the issues and screenshots through the **Mantis bug reporting tool** [2]. Besides the Mantis bug reporting tool, team members discussed specific issues with CFM and WPL via e-mail and online calls.

During the internal testing phase several issues arose and were reported, which are listed in the table below:

Table 3: List of the Osijek demo TC app issues reported during the internal testing

Osijek demo internal testing TC app issues reported				
No.	Issue	Description	Impact	Issue status
1	Impossible TC login issue	The TC app didn't open or respond even after a long waiting time (45 -120 seconds).	crash	Fixed – It was an issue with the authentication service.
2	Slow TC app opening issue	Starting the TC app sometimes took 5 - 15 seconds.	low	Fixed – It was a temporary issue. When there is a high load on the system, login may take longer. Otherwise, it takes only 2 seconds.
3	Preferences - Update issue	3.1. "Preferences" changes could not be remembered, with a screen message: "Preferences couldn't be saved." or the app crashed. 3.2. It took at least three trials to make the same changes for them to be remembered.	high	3.1. Fixed – CFM restarted the preferences module, so that the app could keep the changes. 3.2. To be improved – CFM cleaned up Cloud Wallet, but it still takes a few trials for the module to keep the changes.
4	Preferences - Missing option issue	In the "Preferences" menu, under the "Preferred carrier" submenu, GPP Osijek was not available as an option.	low	Suspended – This section was removed by CFM. Carrier preferences were used in the preceding project and no longer impact the trip search.
5	Identity - Mission "Country" option issue	The "Identity" feature had no option to select "Croatia" as a County.	low	Suspended – The issue/functionality had no impact on testing the app. A new Android library would be needed for Croatia to be listed, which would take too long and extend demo testing deadlines.
6	Identity - User data save not possible issue	When trying to save user data changes, a message appeared on the screen: "Form not valid".	low	Suspended – The functionality did not impact testing the app (Journey Planner, etc.). Since the users got credentials, including a username, they did not need to save additional personal details. CFM needs to change module in the frontend.
7	POIs - Bike sharing stations missing on the map issue	The JP map showed only tram and bus stops as POIs. Bike sharing stations should have	high	Fixed – CFM successfully added Bike sharing stations as POIs to the map by using Excel file describing the

Osijek demo internal testing TC app issues reported				
No.	Issue	Description	Impact	Issue status
		been added to the map.		stations. It improved trip planning.
8	Journey Planner - Long connection search time issue	After entering an origin and destination, in some cases, it took 40 - 60 seconds for a trip to be calculated.	low	No change required – System architecture is designed to support trip planning across the EU, unlike trip planners that cover only one city/country, so longer calculation time is necessary.
9	Journey Planner - Non-logical walking route issue	JP map showed a recommendation for walking to a tram station that was much longer than it should be.	medium	Unable to reproduce – First and list mile rides are calculated based on Open Street Map (OSM). It was a mistake in OSM (data source), so CFM couldn't fix it in the app. No other examples were reproduced, so the impact was low.
10	Preferences & Journey Planner - Preactivated PRM options issue	Sometimes, in the "PRM" (People with reduced mobility) menu, certain options (e.g., old person) were randomly, <i>a priori</i> activated instead of being manually activated by a user. These activations limited trip planning, e.g., bike sharing mode was unavailable in the JP.	high	Fixed – CFM has unchecked/"unactivated" PRM options from their side.
11	Journey Planner - "Unknown lines" and wrong line numbers issue	Sometimes, JP displayed an "unknown line" or incorrect line number/type on a screen instead of a defined, accurate tram or bus line. This issue was due to deviations between the requested data and stop coordinates data from GPP's GTFS file (which caused the inability to find a stop).	high	Partially fixed – CFM modified the requested departure time to 10 seconds earlier than the actual departure time so that there is enough time to walk from a slightly wrong coordinate to a correct coordinate of a stop. GPP's GTFS data contains unprecise data about line numbers and codes, which is an integration issue. It should be improved after the GTFS update in the future.
12	Journey Planner - Not all tram lines displayed/offered	For some calculated and displayed routes, tram lines that could be chosen in real life weren't offered/displayed in the app.	high	Suspended – This was not an app issue but an integration issue. Incorrect departure data is written in GPP's GTFS file. It should be improved after the GTFS update in the future.
13	Journey Planner - Remote bike sharing places issue	In some cases, the bike sharing part of a trip was offered in remote places far away from bike sharing stations.	high	Partially fixed - Mode "allowKeepingRentedBicycleAtDestination" was disabled. Also, the "walkReluctant" mode was integrated into the app, which

Osijek demo internal testing TC app issues reported				
No.	Issue	Description	Impact	Issue status
				shortened long walks to the nearest bike station. To fully fix the issue, the geojson polygon of the existing bike sharing service area (which highly exceeds the bike station area) needs to be sized to a smaller area.
14	Journey Planner - Tram and bus routes displayed as straight-line issue	In some cases, the JP map displayed tram and bus lines only as straight polylines between stops ("cutting" houses where no straight street connects the subsequent stops).	high	Suspended – This is an integration issue, not an app issue. To be improved after the GPP's GTFS file update in the future.
15	My Trips - Saved trips removal issue	Saved trips couldn't be removed (deleted) from the list.	low	Suspended – Saved trips are read from the Cloud Wallet and displayed under "My Trips" but cannot be deleted by the user. This feature should be added in the future.

6.5. Training session

The Osijek demo team organized the **engagement/visibility event with testers on May 26th, 2023, in Cultural Centre Osijek** (address: Kulturni centar Osijek, Ul. Kneza Trpimira 2/A, Osijek). GPP Osijek and Dyvolve organized the event in cooperation with WPL. At the event, representatives of the City of Osijek, TSP GPP Osijek and Dyvolve, Faculty of the University of J.J. Strossmayer, interested citizens, WPL, and the press participated in the use cases demonstration. Twelve participants in total were present at the event.

The aim of the event was to introduce participants to the IP4MaaS project and to **prepare them for the successful testing of the Osijek TC app** in the upcoming week. At the event, participants were instructed on how to use TC functionalities available in Osijek demo.

To better understand the "Trip planner" feature, the Osijek demo team also showed participants different multimodal trip planning use cases/scenarios, i.e., bike-sharing trip, private bike trip, tram trip, bus trip, and combination of bus and bike-sharing the trip, which participants could comment on and give their suggestions.

The Figure below is an example of use case demonstrated at the event.

Primjer 1: Dijeljeni bicikli

Figure 6: Example of bike-sharing use case demonstrated at the event in Osijek.

Besides Osijek demo instructions, other topics were also presented at the event.

Topics that were presented at the event were:

- About TSP GPP Osijek (presented by Mr. Behar Rečica from GPP),
- Introduction to demo testing in Osijek (training) (presented by Mr. Božo Cicvarić and Gordan Topolovec from DL Dyvolve), and
- Experience from previous IP4MaaS demo sites (presented by Ms. Petra Juránková from WPL OLTIS).

Both the User guide and TC app screenshots shown to participants at the engagement event turned out to be beneficial tools, since, during the internal training, the application crashed, was unresponsive, and it was sometimes difficult to demonstrate the use of specific selected functionalities in real time. The guide allowed participants to understand how to use the app and how to behave in case of disruption. Inputs have been given to CFMs based on this internal testing, used for fixing the emerged issues when and if possible.

Figure 7: Engagement event with testers in Osijek (1)

Figure 8: Engagement event with testers in Osijek (2)

Figure 9: Engagement event with testers in Osijek (3)

Figure 10: Engagement event with testers in Osijek (4)

7. Demo execution

Testing period:

Osijek demo execution took place **between 29th May and 2nd June 2023**.

Functionalities tested:

All the functionalities that were planned for testing in preparation phase were successfully tested. The functionalities tested are displayed in a table in 6.1 “Demonstrated functionalities”.

Osijek demo coverage:

Demo testing took place in areas where GPP Osijek public transport service/network is available and in areas where bike-sharing service is available. The covered area included the City of Osijek and its surrounding municipalities Antunovac, Čepin, and Erdut (Bijelo Brdo).

Previous conversational surveys:

Conversational surveys have been distributed by all project partners at the beginning of the project in the framework of WP2, as a preliminary activity to understand needs and expectations from travellers on functionalities provided by a Travel Companion application:

- Interest in the functionality
- Expectations about the functionality

A total of 1027 responses have been collected, not equally distributed in all 6 demo sites. Survey responses have been collected from Athens, Barcelona, Liberec, Padua, Osijek, Warsaw and “others”, a category created for all the responses received from geographical areas not belonging to any demo site (the scope of this conversational survey exercise was to collect the highest number of opinions, and all partners contributed sharing and distributing the conversational survey. That is why responses have been received from demo sites and “other” areas. Overall, the total number of responses received exceeds the minimum target (150 x 6 = 900, responses received: 1027). Therefore, the target defined in the project proposal and project’s starting phase of 150-200 responses per demo site referring to the conversational surveys responses was achieved.

Testers:

Due to the nature of the TC app and technical requirements for demo testers, the primary target groups were students, as they are familiar with the technology and are also one of the main public transport users in Osijek. The testers were mainly students and public transport users.

There were **43 registered testers** (reported by TSP GPP Osijek).

On June 1st, 2023, TSP sent e-mails to testers with the link to fill in USI questionnaires in Croatian and provide feedback about the app. Partner AITEC reported the submission of **41 USI questionnaires**. USI surveys were opened to testers one week after the execution period to get more feedback from the testers.

To attract demo users and increase engagement, TSP provided incentives in the form of a free one-month ticket for public transport operated by TSP.

TSP invited testers to fill in the questionnaire after testing the TC app. By submitting the questionnaire answers, testers automatically acquired a code that they needed to send to the TSP via e-mail to receive the incentive. The incentive included a free one-month public transport ticket (for buses and trams) for the area operated by TSP (City of Osijek and neighboring municipalities).

Although 41 testers submitted the questionnaire answers and automatically became entitled to the incentives, 12 testers in total sent the acquired code to TSP to receive their monthly incentives.

Despite the efforts to increase engagement, the demo testing period in Osijek unfortunately overlapped with the end of the academic year (pupils and students had a lot of obligations to finish their academic year), which impacted their responsiveness and availability to be engaged in the demo.

Communication:

The main communication channel of the Osijek demo team with registered testers during the execution was a dedicated e-mail address previously used for the tester's registration: ip4maas@gpp-osijek.com.

8. Evaluation phase and results

Evaluation of Osijek demo and USI survey results [3]:

- Structure of testers:
 - Of 41 respondents, 34 % were females, and 66 % were males.
- Satisfactory response to **multimodal journey planning testing**, which was one of the main demo objectives:
 - 62% of testers used Journey Planner functionality,
 - 60% of testers used Navigation functionality,
 - Average number of modes involved in the journey per day: 2,
 - Total number of shopped offers/routes planned: 2.277.
- High satisfaction of respondents with the functionalities:
 - 68% of testers were completely satisfied with the Journey Planner function, and
 - 76% of testers were completely satisfied with the Navigation function.
- There was one reported login issue; one tester could not log in with credentials/accounts prepared for Osijek demo testers, even after many trials with different accounts prepared by CFM. The device that the tester used was Google Pixel 5.

Feedback from demo users:

- Journey Planner function is very useful in planning multimodal trips and should become a part of the TSP offerings.
- Future third-party integrations such as other regional bus operators and HŽPP (railway services) should be considered.
- The TC app should be more user-friendly and without unnecessary / non-working functionalities.
- The TC app should be customized for the area of Osijek. It includes additional functionalities unrelated to the Osijek demo site, which creates confusion during its usage.
- The option to purchase integrated PT tickets should be included in the app in the future.

Feedback from demo teams:

- More streamlined user interface (less clicks to execute command) should be used.
- Multimodal journey planning should become the next feature for the transport users.
- Future third-party integrations such as other regional bus operators and HŽPP (railway services) should be considered.
- The TC app should be more stable and functionalities should be focused on Osijek area specifically in order to collect better feedback from users and provide them with a better user experience.

Lessons learned:

- The TC application maturity level and usability are currently low. This makes the TC suitable if its utilization is planned in a research project such as IP4MaaS, where it can be improved with the "learn by doing" method. The feedback provided by the users is important for

improving the app, making some steps further toward its utilization on a much larger commercial scale.

- Defining targeted groups of potential testers (students and PT users in the case of Osijek) is crucial for user engagement as it makes the testing promotion more tailored (it is easier to define communication channels and get better results).
- Promotion on social media is beneficial for user engagement and to increase participation. Osijek demo team noted higher number of registrations after posting information about the demo on social media.
- Providing incentives as a reward for filled surveys is beneficial for user engagement because it motivates testers to participate in testing and send feedback via completed USI questionnaires.
- The testers should be aware of the TC functionalities being tested and participation steps. It is crucial to inform testers that the application is still under development and that not all functionalities will work properly. Engagement events proved to be a good tool for communicating the abovementioned information and for promoting the demo testing.
- The translation of the application can be done more efficiently when the application is known to the translators. Otherwise, the lack of context creates the risk of the translation turning out confusing. It also needs to be tailored for each specific demo site in advance to avoid unnecessary translations.
- Better adaptation of the USI survey to the demo site could provide more relevant results.
- The quality of certain app functionalities also depends on data provided by TSPs and data integration. More time and effort should be foreseen for the data integration phase of the project.
- Although the "Traveller's Feedback" functionality was available for testing in Osijek, the testers did not provide additional comments. To acquire comprehensive feedback from the testers, they should be encouraged in advance to send their comments and thoughts through the app.

9. Conclusions

Osijek was one of six demo sites in the IP4MaaS project where selected S2R IP4 functionalities were successfully tested and demonstrated.

The Osijek demo partners succeeded in obtaining the knowledge and experience of creating a MaaS ecosystem and gathering insight into the usefulness of certain MaaS-related technologies/functionalities, contributing to improved multimodal traveling.

Testing and demonstrating different S2R functionalities, i.e., Individual Last-mile, Navigation, My Trips, added value to public transport users and made it possible for both the Osijek demo team and app users to explore the potential of establishing such a MaaS system.

Demo testing contributed to the successful integration of traditional modes of public transport, i.e., GPP's trams and buses, with innovative e-bike & bike sharing services in Osijek. The service was offered through the Journey Planner function, which was used by more than 60% of the testers. The Journey Planner was the best tested solution demonstrating to the users how their multimodal trips could be eased and emphasizing the advantages of the synergy between bike sharing and public transport.

The feedback from the users was acquired through completed USI questionnaires (41). The testers did not provide additional comments. To collect helpful feedback for the further optimization of the app, users need to be encouraged to provide feedback through different features.

The most common issues during internal testing were login issues, long loading times, not accurately drawn routes on the map, and unknown public transport lines.

To briefly summarize users' opinion, the Travel Companion is an app with high potential as it could attract more people to use sustainable modes of transport and combine them, improving the efficiency of public and shared transportation and reducing GHG emissions. However, scope of functionalities in such a service must be clearly defined based on the technical feasibility and be tailor-made for specific area and target groups. Also, the app development requires constant improvement and refinement based on feedback from demo teams and users, focusing on user experience. Promoting such services is also of great importance and should not be underestimated. Overall, it is very good to have this tool tested as a part of a research project, collecting inputs for refining the ecosystem.

As a conclusion, the technological solutions have a good potential, understood by users, but still need further development and improvement to meet the growing demands for multimodal mobility. Many of the reported bugs and shortcomings were common within all demo sites. Therefore, the reported issues need to be refined and constantly upgraded in the following versions of the Travel Companion. In the project all issues have been communicated to CFMs, who used the inputs collected to work when/if possible, on the ecosystem and improving it for the following demo.

10. References

1. IP4MaaS - IP4 Functionalities and Matrix
2. HAFAS Internet Mantis Tool (<https://mint.hafas.de>)
3. IP4MaaS - T3.2 “User satisfaction with IP4 solutions”; data collected from AITEC (June 2023)